

Synthesis and Properties of α -Phenylcinnamohydroxamic Acids

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HYDROXAMIC acids are versatile reagents for organic and inorganic analysis¹. In the present communication nine new α -phenylcinnamohydroxamic acids (1) have been synthesised.

where $\text{R}^1 = N$ -phenyl, *m*-tolyl, *p*-tolyl or *p*-chlorophenyl
 $\text{R}^2 =$ phenyl, *p*-methoxyphenyl or 3,4,5-trimethoxyphenyl

Preliminary studies show that the acids form a chloroform-extractable violet complex with vanadium(v) in 4 *M* hydrochloric acid solution.

The TG and DTA curves of α -phenylcinnamohydroxamic acids were recorded on a Mettler thermal analyser maintaining the following instrumental factors: TG range, 1 mg full scale sensitivity; DTA range, 50 μV ; heating rate, 8° min^{-1} ; air-flow rate, 100 ml min^{-1} .

The α -phenylcinnamic acids were prepared by the reaction of the respective benzaldehyde with phenylacetic acid and acetic anhydride². The preparations of acid chloride and hydroxylamine are described elsewhere³.

α -Phenylcinnamohydroxamic acids³ (1a-i): A typical preparation of *N*-phenyl- α -phenyl-3,4,5-trimethoxycinnamohydroxamic acid is described. To a mixture of diethyl ether (75 ml), *N*-phenylhydroxylamine (10.9 g, 0.1 mol) and a fine suspensions of sodium bicarbonate (12.6 g, 0.15 mol) in distilled water (25–30 ml) cooled to 0°, was added α -phenyl, 3,4,5-trimethoxycinnamoyl chloride (33.3 g, 0.1 mol) dissolved in benzene (100 ml) dropwise over a period of 50 min. Then the reaction mixture was stirred for additional 30 min and the temperature kept low to prevent possible side-reactions. Some of the products was precipitated as yellow solid while the benzene ether layer was separated and removed under reduced pressure. The yellow residue thus obtained was combined with the precipitated yellow product, triturated for about 15 min with a saturated solution of sodium bicarbonate to remove the acid impurities, filtered, washed with cold water and air-dried (73%), m.p. 111°. Two crystallisation from

a mixture of benzene and petroleum ether gave light yellow compound (65%), m.p. 113°.

Non-aqueous titration: α -Phenylcinnamohydroxamic acid was dissolved in dimethylformamide (50 ml) and titrated with 0.1 *M* sodium methoxide using thymol blue as indicator and potentiometrically by using platinum and calomel electrodes (saturated KCl in methanol) in the presence of nitrogen.

Colorimetric tests¹: The standard vanadium was extracted (in 4 *M* HCl) with a known volume of α -phenylcinnamohydroxamic acid (in chloroform). The violet coloured layer was separated, diluted to 25 ml with chloroform, its absorbance was measured against a reagent blank, and the concentration of hydroxamic acid estimated.

Ionisation constants: These were determined at 25 and 35° in 50, 60 and 70% dioxane-water medium. The procedure and calculation methods are described elsewhere⁴. The ionisation of α -phenylcinnamohydroxamic acid (HA) in aqueous solution gives hydrogen ion and hydroxamate ion and the equilibrium constant may be

$$K_a(\text{aq}) = [\text{H}^+]/[\text{HA}] \cdot Y_{\text{H}^+} \cdot Y_{\text{A}} - / Y_{\text{HA}} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{or } pK_a = -\log[\text{H}^+] + \log[\text{HA}]/[\text{A}] - 2 \log Y_{\pm} \quad (2)$$

Assuming the activity coefficient of unionised acid as unity and the empirical correction for medium 'effect' as suggested by Van Uitert and Haas⁵ and Agrawal⁶,

$$-\log[\text{H}^+] = B + \log U_{\text{H}^+}^2 + \log Y_{\pm} \quad (3)$$

The final form of the equation for calculating the ionisation constants in dioxane-water media is

$$pK_a = B + \log U_{\text{H}^+}^2 + \log [\text{HA}]/[\text{A}] - \log Y_{\pm} \quad (4)$$

where *B* is the pH meter reading and the value of $\log U_{\text{H}^+}^2$ determined experimentally^{4,6}.

In a thermostated condition (25 or 35 ± 0.1°) using a glass electrode and a calomel electrode, 0.25 *M* of α -phenylcinnamohydroxamic acid and the solvent dioxane-water (47.5 ml) were titrated after being deaerated by passage of nitrogen (pre-saturated with solvent), and after 15 min the highest steady *B* value was noted after each increment.

Results and Discussion

The properties of the α -phenylcinnamohydroxamic acids are given in Table 1. The analytical data on hydroxamic acids constants are summarised in Table 2.

The ultraviolet spectra of the acids in 95% ethanol show two distinct bands at around 205 and 277–300 nm. The ratio of $\lambda_{\text{II}}/\lambda_{\text{I}}$ is around 1.4 which is in agreement with that reported earlier^{2,3}. The infrared spectra of the acids show bands at 3 200 (OH), 1 630 (C=O) and for N–O absorption which are similar to those reported earlier³.

The pK_a of α -phenylcinnamohydroxamic acids in 50–70% (v/v) dioxane-water media at 25 and 35°

NOTES

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL, SPECTRAL AND THERMAL DATA OF α -PHENYL CINNAMOHYDROXAMIC ACIDS (1a-i)

Compd. no.	Cinnamohydroxamic acid	M.p. °C	Yield %	λ_{max} nm	$\epsilon \times 10^4$ dm ³ mol ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹	λ_{II}/λ_I	ν_{max} (cm ⁻¹)		DTA (°C)		
							ν_{OH}	$\nu_{C=O}$	Endo	Exo	TG weight loss °C
1a	<i>N</i> -Phenyl- α -phenyl- <i>p</i> -methoxy	109	60	299 205	1.8 3.4	1.46	3 270	1 625	111	315	250-480
b	<i>N</i> - <i>p</i> -Tolyl- α -phenyl- <i>p</i> -methoxy	121	72	299 206	1.7 3.2	1.45	3 140	1 600	123	325	300-500
c	<i>N</i> - <i>m</i> -Tolyl- α -phenyl- <i>p</i> -methoxy	118	62	299 206	1.8 3.8	1.45	3 100	1 635	120	320	295-550
d	<i>N</i> - <i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl- α -phenyl- <i>p</i> -methoxy	122	60	298 205	1.9 3.2	1.44	3 280	1 625	125	330	305-560
e	<i>N</i> -Phenyl- α -phenyl	83	65	279 205	1.6 3.4	1.36	3 160	1 640	85	300	280-510
f	<i>N</i> - <i>p</i> -Tolyl- α -phenyl	113	70	279 206	1.7 3.6	1.35	3 180	1 630	115	318	290-500
g	<i>N</i> - <i>m</i> -Tolyl- α -phenyl	62	60	277 206	1.7 3.6	1.34	3 170	1 630	65	260	240-400
h	<i>N</i> - <i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl- α -phenyl	143	65	277 206	1.8 3.4	1.34	3 140	1 640	145	340	320-600
i	<i>N</i> -Phenyl- α -phenyl-3,4,5-trimethoxy	114	65	300 206	1.6 3.7	1.45	3 160	1 600	115	320	305-590

Compound 1a δ 10.60 (OH), 1.05 (CH=C), 3.60 (J 12.0 Hz, OCH₃); m/z 345 (25.6) M⁺, 330 (15.4) M-NH, 254 (41.0) M-(C₆H₅N-), 237 (92.3) M-(C₆H₅N-OH), 209 (100) M-(C₆H₅N(OH)-C=O); 1b δ 10.5 (OH), 1.05 (CH=C), 2.10 (J 6.0 Hz, CH₃), 3.60 (J 12.5, OCH₃); m/z 360 (6.0) M⁺, 357 (9.5) M-2H, 344 (14.3) M-(NH), 343 (52.4) M-(O), 254 (16.7) M-(CH₃-C₆H₄N-), 237 (100) M-(CH₃-C₆H₄-N-OH), 209 (86.9) M-CH₃-C₆H₄-N(OH)-C; 1c δ 10.7 (OH), 1.05 (CH=C), 2.10 (J 6.2 Hz, CH₃), 3.60 (OCH₃) (J 12.3 Hz, OCH₃); m/z 360 (9.0) M⁺, 357 (17.9) M-(24), 344 (15.4) M-(NH), 343 (66.7) M-(O), 254 (16.7) M-(CH₃-C₆H₄-N-), 237 (96.1) M-(CH₃-C₆H₄-NOH), 2.09 (100) M-(CH₃-C₆H₄N(O)C=O); 1d δ 10.80 (OH), 1.04 (CH=C), 3.58 (J 12.4 Hz, OCH₃); m/z 379 (14.1) M⁺, 377 (15.4) M-(2H), 364 (12.8) M-(NH), 363 (80.0) M-(O), 254 (20.5) M-(ClC₆H₄N), 237 (69.2) M-(ClC₆H₄N-OH), 209 (100) M-(ClC₆H₄NOHCO); 1e δ 10.90 (OH), 1.06 (CH=C); m/z 316 (23.8) M⁺, 300 (20.2) M-(NH), 299 (85.7) M-(O), 212 (35.7) M-(C₆H₅NC), 208 (11.9) M-(C₆H₅-NO), 207 (73.8) M-(C₆H₅NOH), 179 (100) M-(C₆H₅NOHCO); 1f δ 10.6 (OH), 1.05 (CH=C), 1.90 (J 6.1 Hz, CH₃); m/z 330 (30.6) M⁺, 314 (16.5) M-(NH), 313 (63.5) M-(O), 301 (11.9) M-(C=O), 224 (16.3) M-(CH₃C₆H₄N), 212 (21.2) M-(CH₃-C₆H₄NO), 207 (89.4) M-(CH₃C₆H₄NOH), 179 (100) M-(CH₃C₆H₄NOHCO); 1g δ 10.7 (OH), 1.04 (CH=C), 2.0 (J 6.0 Hz, CH₃); m/z 330 (18.8) M⁺, 314 (9.4) M-(NH), 313 (34.5) M-(O), 312 (7.1) M-(OH), 212 (11.9) M-(CH₃-C₆H₄NC), 208 (16.6) M-(CH₃C₆H₄NO), 207 (100) M-(CH₃C₆H₄NOH), 179 (88.1) M-(CH₃C₆H₄NOHCO); 1h δ 10.70 (OH), 1.06 (CH=C); m/z 349 (19.0) M, 334 (20.2) M, M-(NH), 333 (55.9) M-(O), 224 (22.6) M-(Cl-C₆H₄N), 208 (11.9) M-(Cl-C₆H₄NO), 207 (71.4) M-(Cl-C₆H₄NOH), 179 (100) M-(Cl-C₆H₄NOH-CO), 1i δ 10.8 (OH), 1.05 (CH=C), 3.60 (J 12.6 Hz, OCH₃); m/z 405 (1.3) M⁺, 389 (7.7) M-(O), 297 (92.3) M-(C₆H₅-NOH), 270 (12.8) M-(C₆H₅NOCO), 269 (62.8) M-(C₆H₅NOHCO), 78 (100) M-(C₆H₅NOCO), 269 (62.8) M-(C₆H₅NOHCO), 78 (100) M-C₆H₅.

TABLE 2—ANALYTICAL DATA ON α -PHENYL CINNAMOHYDROXAMIC ACIDS (1a-i)

Compd. no.	Non-aqueous titration		Vanadium extraction		Sandell sensitivity $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$
	Mol. wt. found		λ_{max}	ϵ_{max} ($\times 10^3$ dm ³ mol cm ⁻¹)	
	Visual	Potentiometric			
1a	346	345.8	550	6.2	0.008 2
b	361	359.2	550	6.4	0.008 0
c	358	359.7	550	6.3	0.008 1
d	381	379.9	550	6.0	0.008 5
e	316	315.8	550	6.0	0.008 5
f	330	329.1	550	6.2	0.008 2
g	328	329.7	550	6.1	0.008 3
h	350	350.1	550	5.7	0.008 9
i	406	405.3	550	6.3	0.008 2

TABLE 3—THERMODYNAMIC IONISATION CONSTANTS OF α -PHENYL CINNAMOHYDROXAMIC ACIDS AT 25 AND 35°

Compd. no.	pK_a^*					
	$n_2=0.174$ $D=33.0$		$n_2=0.240$ $D=25.37$		$n_2=0.330$ $D=17.54$	
	25°	35°	25°	35°	25°	35°
1a	11.10	10.87	11.85	11.60	12.85	12.60
b	11.36	11.08	12.04	11.80	13.05	12.80
c	11.30	11.05	12.00	11.70	12.96	12.75
d	10.72	10.45	11.40	11.15	12.40	12.15
e	10.75	10.50	11.60	11.35	12.70	12.48
f	10.85	10.60	11.70	11.50	12.93	12.70
g	10.80	10.55	11.65	11.40	12.85	12.60
h	10.50	10.25	11.35	11.10	12.50	12.25
i	11.05	10.82	11.80	11.55	12.80	12.55

* n_2 =mole fraction of dioxane; D =dielectric constant.

TABLE 4—EMPIRICAL CORRELATION BETWEEN pK_a AND MOLE FRACTION OF DIOXANE FOR α -PHENYL CINNAMOHYDROXAMIC ACIDS (1a-i)

Compd. no.	$pK_a = mn_2 + C$					
	25°			35°		
	m	C	r	m	C	r
1a	11.22	9.15	1.00	11.09	8.94	1.00
b	10.86	9.46	1.00	11.04	9.16	1.00
c	10.64	9.45	1.00	10.91	9.14	1.00
d	10.79	8.83	1.00	10.91	8.54	1.00
e	12.49	8.59	1.00	12.69	8.30	1.00
f	13.49	8.49	1.00	13.46	8.26	1.00
g	13.16	8.50	1.00	13.16	8.25	1.00
h	12.82	8.27	1.00	12.82	8.02	1.00
i	11.22	9.10	1.00	11.09	8.89	1.00

are given in Table 3. The average pK_a generally falls within ± 0.02 . The empirical correlation for different mole fractions of dioxane are given in Table 4.

It is observed that the pK_a values of α -phenylcinnamohydroxamic acids are higher at 25° compared to 35° and the value increases linearly with the mole fraction of dioxane due to the decrease in the dielectric constant of bulk solvent. The plot of pK_a versus mole fraction of the dioxane is linear. As the dielectric constant decreases, the ionic dissociation of the proton from the oxygen decreases

TABLE 5 - THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS FOR IONISATION OF α -PHENYLCINNAMOHYDROXAMIC ACIDS (1a-i) AT 25 AND 35°C*

Compd. no.	Mole fraction of dioxan (n_2)								
	0.174			0.240			0.330		
	ΔG°	ΔH°	$-\Delta S^\circ$	ΔG°	ΔH°	$-\Delta S^\circ$	ΔG°	ΔH°	$-\Delta S^\circ$
1a	63.39 (64.18)	40.48	321.50 (321.68)	66.68 (68.49)	44.01	332.16 (332.27)	73.39 (74.39)	44.01	412.29 (412.35)
b	64.88 (65.42)	49.29	218.77 (218.93)	68.76 (69.67)	42.25	372.16 (372.31)	74.53 (75.57)	44.01	428.29 (428.36)
c	64.53 (65.24)	44.01	287.96 (288.15)	68.53 (69.37)	44.01	344.09 (344.21)	74.01 (75.28)	36.96	519.92 (520.12)
d	61.22 (61.70)	47.53	192.11 (192.33)	65.11 (65.83)	44.01	296.10 (296.16)	70.82 (71.73)	44.01	376.22 (376.24)
e	61.39 (61.99)	44.01	243.89 (244.04)	66.25 (67.01)	44.01	312.09 (312.18)	72.53 (73.68)	38.72	474.46 (474.51)
f	61.96 (62.58)	44.01	251.89 (252.05)	66.82 (67.90)	35.20	443.72 (443.84)	73.84 (74.98)	40.48	468.14 (468.27)
g	61.88 (62.29)	44.01	250.77 (248.11)	66.53 (67.31)	44.01	316.02 (316.25)	73.39 (74.39)	44.01	412.29 (412.35)
h	59.97 (60.52)	44.01	223.97 (224.09)	64.82 (65.53)	44.01	292.03 (292.09)	73.39 (72.32)	44.01	384.22 (384.25)
i	63.11 (63.88)	40.48	317.57 (317.61)	67.39 (68.19)	44.01	328.09 (328.20)	73.10 (74.10)	44.01	408.22 (408.41)

* ΔG° and ΔH° are in kJ mol^{-1} and ΔS° is in $\text{JK}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1}$; values in parentheses are at 35°.

to a greater extent than the ion-dipole interaction between the proton and the solvent molecule. When the $\text{p}K_a$ values of α -phenylcinnamohydroxamic acids are plotted against $1/D$, where D is the dielectric constant of the medium, a distinct curvature is observed.

The ΔG° , ΔH° and ΔS° data are given in Table 5. It is observed that there is a general tendency of increase in magnitude of ΔS° with the increase in dioxane content of the solvent.

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